

THE FOHATIC FLUID

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Abstract: The “germinating of life” is Fohat; Fohat is the active principle of all material form; For this, Fohat is a “fluid” that, in its viscosity and/or wateriness, can “penetrate” the entire corpuscle, impregnating everything. This essay intends to present, in general terms, how “Fohat”, as a “divine fluid”, permeates all matter, spiritualizing it (“electrifying” it). Our method is phenomenological. And our hypothesis is that if there is life in all matter; that which makes it “alive”, esoterically speaking, is “Fohat”.

Keywords: Fluid. Fohat. Matter. Spirit.

Introduction

At the beginning of *Secret Doctrine*, Vol. 1, by H. P. Blavatsky ([1888] (2020)), there is a statement that says that Fohat interconnects, through the Perpetual Movement of Life, all things of *Conscience* and, on the other hand, all things *Nature*. With the *Conscience*, Fohat, with its dynamic or mysterious act, *unifies* the Consciousness or Universal Mind to *individual consciences* of all beings. And, for *Nature*, *unifies* all Matter to Mind, making it *existing*. It can be seen, then, at a first glance, that the creation of a Being called Fohat by God is of paramount and essential importance for just one simple thing - the absolute, eternal and infinite connection with ALL things in all the worlds, especially , those here on Earth. The planet rotates within its orbit, and Fohat is there and here, sometimes in a distant point on the planet's surface, sometimes in its center, or even sometimes omnisciently, in its entire structure. Therefore, it is worth noting that his act, despite being universal and eternal, is pure and profound. Pure and profound, like a symphony that touches the soul or a simple poem that keeps within itself a record of the depths of the world. And here, we open the first question - “why, Lord, does modern man not have eyes for this *extraordinary*?” The world sighs, breathes, sweats; It is the Breath of Life! Exactly how beings do. Beautiful God, what Glory is Yours, that the Sublime is not accessible to all men, especially those with a rude, cold and selfish heart. How much Beauty, Lord, there is in your gesture, which to see such things requires a pure and sweet heart, like the proliferation of the perfume of a rose as its petals open in a

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voluptuous way, spreading its sweet charm in the Fire of the Space of the Abstract . And, here, the key concept of Fohat's mysterious dynamics - *the Abstract*. Of Fohat's glorious act is of such magnitude that we wonder - "Is Fohat really a Being"? Even so, despite being a Being, he *has no shape*, because the form itself is the form that is the Abstract of the World. Non-abstraction. Yes, *Abstract*. Because "Abstraction" is more in the field of complexifying a phenomenon. The Concept of Abstract comes from Latin *Abstract* which justifies only that which is only *the Abstract, in its essence*. Thus, Fohat is imperious, masterful and sublime. So, on this occasion, we will try to go in-depth *in the invisibility of the transcendental and divine dynamics of each of his acts* at first but forms the entire element and yet, tirelessly, *coat and introjecting* the bottom of every form of a *content* that would be *the phohatic fluid, eternal and infinite, of the cosmicity of the energy of the Cosmos*. This is precisely why the title of this essay (*The fohatic fluid*) justifies our meeting with *the contact* with *this fluid* that no that just does *densify* every natural element of *Nature* or the *Conscience*, but it causes *the beautiful vibratory movement of all its particles* deep down deep inside your *interior*. How, then, does this fund *vibrates*? How, then, does Fohat make him *vibrate*? We will then try to achieve *this background* which, luckily, can only *be lightened* with the *light* originating from his pure act. So, what is this made of? *vibration*? Where does this come from? *Spirit of Life* What is Fohat? What mystery is this that everything, in an absolute act, is everything everything? In this mysterious dynamic, does Fohat encounter Time, or Space? If not, he is in *interstice* or in *interval* like Leibnizian monads? Is Fohat at the same time the opening and the fluid itself introjected there? But how so? In a word, if everything in the universe originates from Perpetual Motion, Fohat is, par excellence and essentially, *the Movement*? However, here, we present, among a multitude of aspects about Fohat, a single point, namely, - "How '*ideas*' of the Universal Mind are *printed* in matter by the fohatic fluid?"

The "fluid"

In science, "fluid" can be defined as a substance that *deforms* (or that "dilutes") easily and continuously in contact with a "force" or "tension". For example, in contact with fire at high temperatures (as in the case of "iron" at high temperatures, *transform* in a superheated orange fluid). The metal sheet in the emergence of fire dilutes continuously and completely, depriving its previous substance that was "solid" into a consistent, burning and "watery" liquid. We can remember here the natural phenomenon of volcanoes that "expels" fire larvae into the air, causing them to contain an immensity of "burning aqueous liquid". In this sense, the "fluid" would be, in nature's formulation, the best example of a type of "substance" that, while it goes *draining* As its "viscous liquid" also surrounds material things, it also prints a "mark" on the "fabric" of these

things. Just like thinking, like *abstract entity*, *penetrates* and *permeates* space with its “psychic currents”, the “fluid” *penetrates* any body and/or surface that is like “water” that *pervades* any matter, leaving *printed* its “watery mark” on a given matter. A clear experiment is to put “sugar” in a metal pan and heat it to a certain temperature - the “sugar” substance *will immediately transform* into a yellowish “fluid”. This shows us that not only “sugar”, but any solid substance and/or material will suffer the *effects* from a “burning mass” to transforming into a “liquid”.

Which means that if the universe *warm up* in an abrupt, unbridled and constant way, at some point in the history of nature, the entire terrestrial material mass, that is, everything that has a “material nature” became *would transform*, all at once, in one *Large Aqueous Substance*. The pre-Socratics, such as Thales of Miletus (625 BC), believed that the universe as we see it was entirely created from the element “water” and, we believe here, that not only its origin, but also its end will also be its “dissolution” in “living water”. In a broad perspective, it is as if all the matter in the world were contained or carried within itself, in a *very deep interiority*, a “watery liquid”. In other words, it is as if each corpuscle of matter (solid or not), that is, the entire “substance”, was composed of a “fluidic material”. As in the example of “sugar”, it would have to contain, from the outset, a “fluidic mass” that, upon contact with heat, would “awaken” such fluidic particles. This can demonstrate to us that every solid and/or material body is also composed, inside, of “water”. In the context of human beings, there would not be a better example. The entire “organic” human organism is made up of 70% water and, we believe, this percentage is quite *bigger* because the blood flow that *passes* throughout our organism depends, essentially and by nature, on the element “water” to simply “exist”. In other words, the entire “organic” element is composed of water, air, fire and earth, at least within the Earth. These four elements make up, as we know, *terrestrial nature*. In this sense, it is almost impossible, for human understanding, to define or even conjecture which of these elements is the most primordial, that is, which of them bears or presents the cause and/or first substance of the appearance of things. From another perspective, it is “water” as a “fluid” that *dissolve* completely any *point* of the atmosphere, transforming this “point” into more “water”, that is, into a greater accumulation of liquid in the terrestrial environment.

As in the universe everything is transformed and is never created or destroyed, this is true precisely, in this case, because of “water” as a primordial element. The “Primordial Light” clearly comes before the four essential elements, however, “water” is the secondary element of the terrestrial environment when planet Earth, in its immensity, is more composed of “water” than “earth”; because everything that *appears* in the universe as “earth” it is a matter, in its essence, also “aqueous”. In this sense, every “material” compound is, in essence, “fluidic” because “water” is its compound *primordial*. Thus, of the four elements, we know that “water” and “fire” would be the best known not because they are most “present” in the atmosphere, but because they are, in our

material and limited perception, those that we “see” the most. For example, in the Christian tradition, the element “air” would represent, in essence, the “Holy Spirit”. How is it possible, with Creation, that God created only “four elements” which, in their *synthesis* and in your *essence*, *contemplate* practically *all*. And it's incredible to see how *such elements* together “synthesize” practically *all phenomena of the terrestrial environment* (and if not the entire universe like the other planets). On the other hand, in the Eastern tradition, one can still speak of the “Waters of Space” in the sense that it was “these waters” that *drew* and *covered* the whole atmosphere *material* and *space* that we know today and in which we live. Space would be, in Gabriel’s view (2017, p. 79, emphasis mine), “the *origin* and others *memory* of all things that are and were.” Therefore, if “water” as “fluid” *transform*; This essentially means that it neither creates nor destroys, but turns the old form into a *new form*. Perhaps this is the most complete meaning of “fluid”, just like “fire”, “water” as it transforms a form, being at the same time *transcending* because, in this “transcendence”, “water”, as a primordial element, is always “above” and/or “beyond” the entire material compound. In this, the presumption that the universe will never end, but if *will transform...* And, in this sense, the “earth” would not be the cause of this because the “earth” being an “absolutely material body” is already part of the entire “Substance of the World”; It would also not be the “air”, as this, despite its “winds”, would do nothing more than “make move” the entire “Structure of the World”. On the other hand, it would either be the “fire” that turns everything into ashes (any material body), or it would be the “water” that turns the entire material body into more “water”. “Fire” or “water” would be the cause of the origin, as well as the end of the world.

Every material compound is made up of “water”; which means that “any organism, organic or not” is composed, in essence, of “water”. What this demonstrates is precisely *the substrate of all things*. Having a material body, its interior is a “watery liquid”, but why? Because, as a simple and ordinary example, if we “subtract” the juice from a fruit such as an “orange”, it will immediately be separated and/or produce a “liquid”, just as we separate a “secretion” in our body and ends up producing a “wateriness”. To say that every organic compound is made, properly and in essence, of “water”. This same “water” as a “fluid” can also, with the magnetism of the “emitted word”, “transform” into “holy water”, as this phenomenon is as if the water itself contained within itself an “unknown energy” that was also absorbed by the air of the vocabulary mass. In this sense, it is as if the “word”, more than the “thought”, *to have turned around, to have penetrated and impregnated* all “aqueous substance” in its essence and, for a *reaction* unknown, the “water” became “pure water”. As well as the opposite, in the emission of “negative” words that “water” would become a “dark or tenebrous compound”. This is why phenomena such as “magnetism” and “electricity” are still almost completely “unknown” today simply because, as esotericism already states, the entire space of the entire atmosphere has, in its composition, *invisible magnetic and electrical fluids* as, in the

sense of Helena Roerich (1930), a *Great Cosmic Magnet*. In this sense, “human” words are very flawed when they, in their essence, are absolutely “extraordinary”. Even in the containment of a spirit of divine intellect, that is, by the simple fact that we are “similar to God”, as in the example of the “manifestation of water”, modern man has not reached 10% of the discovery of all wonders and mysteries of creation that has yet to be deciphered.

The “ideas” of the Universal Mind imprinted on matter by the fohatic fluid

Already *introduction* In this essay, we present some characteristics about *Fohat*. Here, as we promised, we will say a few words about - “how *ideas* of the Universal Mind are *printed* in matter by the phohatic fluid”. I noticed this thought in the book *The Eternal Ether*, by Douglas Gabriel (2017). This one says - “Behind all matter *a spirit is donated* which is held suspended in space and time for the purpose of humans giving birth *an independent conscience*” (GABRIEL, 2017, p. 41). This “spirit” is *Fohat*. In this context, *Fohat* would be the “Being” or “Substance” that *it hurt* the process of “awakening of matter by the spirit” (the “electrification” of every material body) so that humans *realized*, with his intellect, that “in all matter ‘life’ coexists”. In this regard, *Fohat* is the “being” that gives birth, that is, *awaken* in all matters its “spirituality”. Since ancient times, mystics have believed that this process of “spiritualization” has been happening in the universe since God created the world. *Cosmos*. Much like Leibniz's monads, *Fohat* and the *living being* which ends up “covering” everything and assigning, at each point of life (understood as “matter”), a *life of spirit*. According to occultists, *Fohat* was responsible for the *spirituality* of the worlds. Thus, *Fohat* giving and/or attributing “light” to the airs of all life in matter would make this matter itself a *independent consciousness*. For, for occultists, matter is also “consciousness”. In other words, *Fohat* is responsible for “awakening” the *spirit* of matter, in this case, “electrifying” it. *The manifestation of the quintessence of the spirit*.

In the esoteric view, *Fohat* is, then, the dynamic energy of the *Cosmic Ideation* or, in a word, the *Divine Thought*, par excellence. In this tradition, *Fohat* is the *quite*; the means through which everything *flows* and the medium “between” all matter (“flows” - “fluid”). In this sense, all *impulse* which, by nature, is “dynamic”, *Fohat* finds itself *in it*. Once again, we remember the “Leibnizian monads” which, similar to *Fohat*, are found in the “bond” of the essences of things. According to tradition, *Fohat* would be the soul principle *cheering* every atom as well as all life. It would also be the electrical power of *affinity* and *tuning* of all *forces* and *energies*. *Fohat* can be water, air, fire or earth. *Fohat* would be both above and below (Hermes Trismegistus). Of all the substance created *Fohat* would be the “active principle”. In a broad sense, *Fohat* would be *the interiority of all things*

or, in other words, *the brilliance of the fire of all matter*. As everything in the universe comes down to matter, both its organic life and its spiritual life are due to the dynamic and transcendental act of Fohat. In a very broad but profound vision, Fohat would be the *transcendental unity* of all the forces and energies of the universe, as, on the other hand, the monad, would be the *synthesis* of everything, both the beginning and the end. Fohat emits the creative and creative ray of light as it permeates all matter. Thus, the “ideas” of the Universal Mind or the Mind of God can only “take effect” in any way with the *first impulse* from the act of Fohat to *cheer* all matter. If, in our view, *Fohat* and the *active ingredient* in all matters; all matter would only have “substantial life” from the *phohatic animating act*. In this context, *Fohat* would be the first impulse of nature that *league* “spirit” and “matter” in the first stages of their “differentiation”.

If everything in the universe is “energy”, *Fohat* and you *energizing principle* (and therefore “encouraging”). According to the Secret Doctrine of H. P. Blavatsky ([1888] (2020)), the universe arose from a curious phenomenon of the Primordial Epoch known as “Cosmic Pre-Ideation”; period in which the “ideas” of the Mind of God were “projected” into the Body of the World, giving rise to all kingdoms and natures. So, in this sense, *Fohat* would be the “intermediary angel” who *interspersed* this divine act of creation when, in the powerful and kind act of God, *Fohat*, fed by the first impulse of the Light of Life, gives rise to the spiritualization of all elements of nature, including all matter. Since Fohat is a powerful force of *energization*, he was responsible for “awakening” all substances in the world from their primordial sleep. In order to confirm this thought of ours, Gabriel (2017, p. 98) also states “The manifested universe is the result of the interaction of Cosmic Ideation with Cosmic Substance and Fohat originates from this *interaction*”. In Cosmic Ideation, the *archetype* of the “idea” of the formation of the universe could only be “animated” and “imprinted” on the world of all matter through *Fohat*. Fohat is then in *spirituality*, called “fluid” to remember what we previously said was the element “water”, the primordial condition of all the “breath of life”. Regarding matter, the “fohatic fluid” would be the “intersection” or the primordial “interval” between the two planes of life - “the material” and “the spiritual”. In other words, it would be both in the “soul” of things and in the “density” of things, located in the *center* of all of them.

Fohat, by animating the atoms of all substances, *soul* also yours *spirit*. In this sense, the universe as we “see” and “perceive”, its “animate” form and content, is nothing more *effect* of the phohatic fluid. This *fohatic fluid floats* through “between” and “inside” the substances of things, *awakening* the manifestation of the universe to our “perceptual views”. For example, the *colorful* of a peacock's feathers is Fohat, the original transmitting and animating principle, together with the ethereal force that together makes *cheer* all. If a “light” shines in an “intelligent being”, Fohat would be the origin of this “light” together, of course, with the luminescence of the created fire of

the divine intellect of that creature as a “created substance”. In another sense, the fohatic fluid would be the “informal” and/or “invisible” energy within the entire *manifested form*. This “fluid”, impregnating matter, turns “dead” matter into “living” matter. It would be more or less like this: “for everything that is essentially ‘organic’, Fohat would be responsible”. In the Eastern tradition, Fohat, as an intermediary force that permeates every material body, would make a “condensed or coagulated matter” (*Mulaprakriti*) into “active, freed and/or energized matter” (*Prakriti*).

Like “light”. The “light”, in its essence, is a dense and coagulated light, in the Eastern tradition, Fohat would be the “force” or the “being” that, with its “fluid”, would “dilute” this “dense and embodied matter” into “active and released force”, precisely because of the “viscosity” of the “immaterial fluid” that permeates and impregnates, in its “energetic” mode, the substance of “light”. Blavatsky ([1888] (2020)) once said - “The cause of the world is the *luminosity*; luminosity is the *Universal Void*”. Let's see, if every being "has" contact with the world primarily through "light", without Fohat, the "light" would also be a Great Void, since all the corpuscles of "electricity" and "magnetism" are donated from the fohatic and/or Cosmic Substance. In very broad terms, the phohatic fluid would participate in the entire *fluidification* of all states of matter on planet Earth; in this case; would be the process of *dematerialization* to “insert” your *spiritualization*. Thus, the “light”, itself, is everywhere in space, however, this peculiar manifestation would only be possible thanks to matter and/or etheric fluid (Fohat). According to Gabriel (2017), it is in empty space where reality itself exists, that is, where there are atoms, space is “hollow” and/or “empty” without the manifestation of the “ethereal” and/or phohatic being. Therefore, it would be the “phohatic fluid” that would make the “atoms” fully active.

Thus, the very states of matter are in a *zero-point* or a *non-space* whose *ethereal virtue* it is the mysterious force that transforms “pure emptiness” into “living presence”. As Gabriel (2017, p. 128-129) states - “according to spiritual development, we perceive a new world that seems to unfold for our own being; we feel like there is a *Large Organism* - a “Being” - within which we live.” Then, *what* or *who* Could this be a “Great Organism”? In this case, they could be, in the plural, *the etheric formative forces* that, according to Gabriel (2017, p. 129, my emphasis), “the cosmic etheric rhythms *resonate* within human organs and bodily systems. This harmonic resonance communicates between the human etheric and cosmic bodies.” God manifests himself through an unmanifested act of His, that is, on the other hand, all created substances “manifest themselves” not by virtue of their “matter”, but, essentially, by virtue of their “spirit”. Because the “spirit” is that of the “unmanifested”, that is, that which is exempt from any state of matter. The very “being 'state' of a matter” involves some type of “vitalizing energy” and also an “independent consciousness” and, in this case, the etheric and/or phohatic formative forces are the primordial “glimpse” of its “manifestation”. . Thus, “space”, “time” and “matter”, in mystical saying, can only *really*

“manifest” itself through “forces” and/or “energies” that “stimulate” it. This “force” and/or “energy” is *Fohat*.

For example, “sound” is, in essence, a “living and/or organic being” that “manifests” itself throughout the environment precisely through its phenomenon of *materialization* and *dematerialization*. When a sound *soa*, it is already another type of matter and when this sound corpuscle reaches the organ of auditory perception, it is also another type of matter because *suffered* the effects of its own “dematerialization”. Thus, we see the concept of “matter” as something “dense”, “opaque” and/or devoid of “life”. But, in fact, in the near future, science will discover (as it is already discovering) how many infinite states of *materialization* of “matter” itself. Soon, the “germination of things in life” may no longer be a great mystery as it still is today. In this sense, every act, material and/or immaterial, *stay registered no organism of nature* because Fohat, as a “viscous fluid”, receives all *impressions* of this act, thus, according to Gabriel (2017, p. 150), “everything that man does is inscribed in the fabric of the cosmos and the cosmos is reflected in nature”. Therefore, the entire act is invested with a “ray of light” as if we could “see” spiritual beings with our organs of light (GABRIEL, 2017, p. 152). It's incredible, but we have such an extraordinary capacity that we can “see”, with the eyes of the spirit, the process by which “light” begins to illuminate plants and living beings. This is possible not only because of our “organ of perception”, but because, as divine “creatures”, we were made of “light” and for “light”. Or, on the other hand, we can “see” how they are “constructed” *somewhere inside us* a series of stream of thoughts. Both this act and that one are the result of the “etheric fluid” or, if you prefer, “fohatic”.

Conclusion

In short, at the level of conclusion, we can say that empirical science is today, in the 21st century, well strengthened and even well founded, but, in “materialist” and/or “formal” terms, incapable of *testify* things like what we present here. But, thank God, as man is, in his essence, “infinite”; “infinite” are his capabilities of his “intellective power” when, even in his “supernatural imagination and creativity”, he “co-creates” multiple and possible “realities” of “life” and “existence”. While plants and animals, from their birth, *live* of the constant vibration of etheric formative forces (*Fohat*) such as, for example, the *Solar Logos*, on the other hand, man, in his ignorance that becomes “absolute”, makes *get sick* him, the universe and all creatures with their tremendous “lack of knowledge” regarding creation. May we, in this particular incarnation, *testify* as an “incarnated being”, things like the “spirit of matter” or the “soul of things”, making it absolutely certain that our God exists and created everything in the most perfect way possible.

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